

The attraction of brown planthoppers and green leafhoppers to colored lights

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To study the attraction of brown planthoppers and green leafhoppers to colored lights, observations were made using petromax lights covered with yellow, green, and red shades. The lights were distributed October to December

Attractiveness of colored lights to brown planthoppers and green leafhoppers at Aduthurai, India.

Light color	Trapped brown planthoppers (no.)				Trapped green leafhoppers (no.)			
	Oct	Nov	Dec	Total	Oct	Nov	Dec	Total
Yellow	6036	442	78	6556	5073	355	127	5555
Green	2937	188	40	3165	1634	178	72	1884
Red	2409	235	36	2680	1397	220	67	1684

1979 on the bunds of paddy fields every night from 1800 to 2000 hours. Insect pests trapped in water with a few drops of kerosene in a tray around the lights were collected and identified (see table).

Both insect pests were more active

during October than during November and December. Yellow attracted considerably more brown planthoppers and green leafhoppers than did green and red. ■

Time of transplanting and gall midge incidence in Manipur

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Time of transplanting and incidence of gall midge were studied during the 1979-80 insect outbreak in Imphal West. Three highly susceptible rice varieties received no pesticide application. Fifty hills per variety, replicated four times, were sampled. Percentage silver shoots was calculated as the ratio of number of silver shoots to number of tillers per 50 hills at maximum tillering.

The later the planting date, the higher the gall midge incidence (see table). The State Department of Agriculture currently recommends transplanting the test varieties in June and July. However, by June gall midge incidence is already high. ■

Time of transplanting and incidence of gall midge in 3 varieties in Imphal, India.^a

Time of transplanting	Silver shoots (%)			
	Punshi	Phouoibi	IR24	Average
2d week June	10.81 (10.98)	6.83 (15.06)	8.12 (16.48)	8.59
3d week June	15.21 (22.37)	12.05 (19.93)	12.96 (21.07)	13.41
4th week June	24.63 (29.42)	17.96 (25.00)	17.36 (24.27)	19.98
1st week July	26.13 (30.71)	20.36 (25.85)	21.09 (26.73)	22.52
2d week July	28.03 (31.97)	22.52 (28.33)	27.02 (31.20)	25.86
3d week July	37.03 (37.29)	27.80 (31.83)	31.94 (34.05)	32.26
CD (P = 0.05)	9.65	7.73	8.89	

^aFigures in parentheses are transformed angular values.

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Effect of custard-apple oil and neem oil on the life span of and rice tungro virus transmission by *Nephotettix virescens*

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Most insect damage results from direct feeding or indirect transmission of pathogenic organisms during feeding. Antifeedant chemicals offer a novel approach to pest control. Seed oils of

neem *Azadirachta indica* and custard-apple *Annona* sp. possess marked anti-feedant properties. These plants are widespread in many rice-growing countries in South and Southeast Asia.

Oils were emulsified with 0.1% liquid detergent and tested at 5 concentrations (5, 10, 20, 30, and 50%). Crude neem seed oil was expelled from decorticated seeds obtained from India. Custard-apple seed oil was obtained by methanolic extraction of seeds obtained at IRRI. Ten-day-old TN1 rice seedlings were sprayed 3 hours before they were

exposed to the viruliferous vector insect. Control plants were sprayed with a 0.1% detergent solution. Treated seedlings were placed in glass test tubes (15 × 1.5 cm) and covered with polyvinyl caps.

Viruliferous insects used were *N. virescens* adults reared on virus-free 45-day-old TN1 rice plants and allowed 4-day acquisition feedings on source plants. A viruliferous insect was released into each test tube for inoculation feeding. After 24 hours, the viruliferous insect was transferred to another freshly treated seedling and inoculated seedlings

were transplanted in pots for disease development. Successive inoculation and access feeding on treated plants continued until the death of all the viruliferous insects. Symptoms in inoculated seedlings were observed on day 12.

The randomized complete-block design experiment was replicated 5 times using 440 viruliferous insects and 440 treated seedlings for 11 treatments. A total of 2,200 viruliferous insects and 4,667 treated seedlings were used.

Both oils reduced insect survival and RTV transmission. One day after feeding, 95.5% of the insects survived in the control. Survival was significantly less on all oil-sprayed plants — the higher the oil concentration, the lower the insect survival (Table 1) — but differences in insect survival at different oil concentrations were not significant.

Two days after feeding, insect survival on the control averaged 86.5%. In the custard-apple oil treatment at 30% concentration, only 1.5% of the insects survived; at 50% concentration, none survived. In neem oil treatments, 2.5% of the insects survived at both concentrations. Three days after feeding, insect survival was near zero in most treatments.

Transmission of RTV by the viruliferous insect to oil-sprayed TN1 rice seedlings was represented by the number of infected seedlings. One-day inoculation feeding infected 60.4% of the control seedlings. Infection of oil-sprayed

Table 1. Survival of *Nephotettix virescens* after 1, 2, and 3 days exposure to TN1 rice seedlings sprayed with oils^a at IIRRI.

Oil concentration (%)	Survival (%) of <i>N. virescens</i> ^b					
	1 d		2 d		3 d	
	C-ao	No	C-ao	No	C-ao	No
5	25.0 b	57.5 b	5.0 b	23.5 b	0	7.0 b
10	27.5 b	36.5 cd	5.5 bc	16.5 bc	0.5 b	5.5 b
20	22.5 bc	42.0 c	6.0 b	8.0 bc	1.0 b	0 b
30	16.5 bc	34.0 cd	1.5 b	2.5 c	0 b	0 b
50	1.5 c	26.6 d	0 b	2.5 c	0 b	0 b
0 (control: water + 0.1% liquid detergent)	95.5 a	95.5 a	86.5 a	86.5 a	80.0 a	80.0 a

^aC-ao = custard-apple oil, No = neem oil. ^bIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Table 2. Rice tungro virus (RTV) infection on TN1 rice seedlings sprayed with oils^a after 1 and 2 days exposure to viruliferous insects at IIRRI.

Oil concentration (%)	RTV infection (%) of TN1 seedlings ^b			
	1 d		2 d	
	C-ao	No	C-ao	No
5	25.0 b	27.0 b	6.9 b	13.6 b
10	19.0 bc	16.4 bc	4.2 b	11.2 b
20	19.0 bc	20.9 bc	2.4 b	10.2 b
30	20.4 bc	13.6 c	11.0 b	4.5 b
50	10.5 c	11.8 c	0.2 b	10.3 b
0 (control: water + 0.1% liquid detergent)	60.4 a	60.4 a	35.5 a	35.5 a

^aC-ao = custard-apple oil, No = neem oil. ^bIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

seedlings was significantly less at all concentrations of both oils (Table 2).

After 2 days of inoculation feeding, 35.5% of the control seedlings were infected; significantly less infection occurred in all oil treatments. Both oils at 5% concentration significantly

reduced RTV infection of TN1 seedlings, on par with infection levels at higher concentrations. After 3 days of feeding, only a few plants were infected. After 4 days of feeding, no seedlings were infected because no insects survived on oil-sprayed plants. ■

Effect of foliar insecticides on stem borers and leaffolders

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The effect of six foliar insecticides on rice stem borers and leaffolders was studied at Tirur during the 1980-81 samba season. The field trial was laid out in a simple randomized block design with three replications. IR8 seedlings 35 days old were planted in 12-m² plots at 20 × 10-cm spacing. Insecticides were sprayed at 45 and 60 days after transplanting (DT).

Deadhearts (stem borer damage) in

Effect of new foliar insecticides on rice stem borers and leaffolders. Tirur, India. 1980-81 samba.

Treatment	Formulation	Quantity applied (kg a.i./ha)	Stem borer deadhearts 75 DT		Leaffolder damage 15 DT		Grain yield (t/ha)
			No.	Square root	%	Angles	
			Carbosulfan	24 EC	0.4	18.8	
Bendiocarb	80 WP	0.5	12.0	3.47	2.5	9.03	6.1
BPMC	20 EC	0.5	26.9	5.19	23.9	29.29	5.1
Acephate	75 SP	0.5	6.8	2.61	4.2	11.76	6.1
Vamidothion	30 EC	0.5	37.6	6.13	35.8	36.79	3.9
Ethion	50 EC	0.5	29.8	5.46	48.2	43.95	3.1
Control	—	—	35.5	5.96	68.9	56.11	1.8
CD	—	—	—	1.32	—	9.52	1.5

each plot and leaf damage (leaffolders) on 50 hills/plot were assessed at 75 DT (see table). Bendiocarb, acephate, and carbosulfan were more effective in

checking both stem borer and leaffolder. Their use gave higher yields than did three other chemicals and no treatment. ■